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STEM4GirlsUC3M: reducing gender gap in engineering

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ABSTRACT

In the last years, the number of engineering vocations has been reduced. In Spain, according to the competent Ministry, the variation rate in the last 10 years is -28.7%. This decrease is even greater in the case of women. In Engineering and Architecture studies, only the 25.6% are women.

Since 2016, in the EPS Polytechnic School of the Carlos III University of Madrid we have been working on several initiatives to reduce this problem, which have been unified in 2018 under the global project STEM4GirlsUC3M. The target audience is high-school girls between 12 and 18 years old. The action lines are (1) mentoring programs; (2) scenic arts to raise awareness about the problem; (3) technological workshops and experiences, named Tech-Fridays, given by university teachers and researchers, (4) technological contests and, finally (5) sessions with relatives.

Regarding mentoring programs, we have selected the Technovation Challenge international program from Iridescent (non-profit organization) and the STEMTalentGirl program from ASTI Talent and Technology Foundation. Furthermore, we also developed our own technological workshops and experiences, in which the high-school girls can experiment with technology and improve their knowledge about it.

The global project will be evaluated through surveys and interviews to the participants.

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1 INTRODUCTION

In 2010, the UNESCO published the “Engineering: Issues, Challenges, and opportunities for Development” report [1] produced in conjunction with the World Federation of Engineering Organizations (WFEO), the International Council of Academies of Engineering and Technological Sciences (CAETS), and the International Federation of Consulting Engineers (FIDIC). This report shows the value of engineering to transform the world we live in, and to improve our quality of life. Only in sub-Saharan Africa, it is estimated that 2.5 million new engineers and technicians will be needed, to be able to guarantee the access to drinking water and sanitation of infrastructures. The report warns that despite this, in many regions of the world there was a reduction in the interest of young people, especially young women, in engineering, science and technology studies. Without engineers, there is no engineering; without engineering, the sustainable development of our planet will stop. Therefore, it is fundamental to break this trend and get more young people want to be engineers. For this, it is necessary to transform the education, both in the curriculum and in the methodologies. We must also address the important gender gap that clearly is one reason that aggravates the problem.

Despite the many initiatives that have been developed in recent years, they have not been able to reduce this lack of vocations in most countries and the gender gap in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) studies has been aggravating. In 2017, the UNESCO once again published the report “Cracking the code: Girls' and women's education in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM)” [2] with the aim of trying to understand the reasons that lead to this situation and, above all, to give recommendations on what should be done. The report emphasizes that the *“research on biological factors, including brain structure and development, genetics, neuroscience and hormones, shows that the gender gap in STEM is not the result of sex differences in these factors or in innate ability”*. Studies [3] suggest that girls, although they seem to freely choose not to study these subjects, do so more because of self-selection biases that result from the explicit and implicit stereotypes that have been instilled into them since childhood. Many times even in their closest family environment. The representation of women made by the media and the state of society in terms of gender equality also exert a very important influence.

There is clear evidence [4] that working with girls at an early age, these tendencies can be reversed so that this selection is truly vocational and not conditioned by biases. Among the lines of action that are recommended, one is to work with girls by doing practical activities in laboratories, relating what is done in these practices with their real application and with the social impact that they entail. Another one is to involve girls in mentoring programs, because they encourage their confidence, motivation and improve their understanding of STEM careers. Several works in recent years also speak about the importance of visualizing female referents in STEM areas, to be “role models” for them. Some studies [5][6] also suggest that women, in general, prefer to develop their professional job in areas with a strong

content of social commitment, hence their predilection for studies in the fields of Health and Education. However, as we have said, if there is anything that has changed the world for the better in recent years, it is the advances in the STEM disciplines. In fact, the 2030 Sustainable Development Agenda considers that STEM fields will have a fundamental role in the transformation that will allow compliance with this Agenda.

In 2018, SEFI published a Position Paper [7] in which it states that “*diversity, equality and inclusiveness are essential to enriching engineering education experiences and generating innovations that can drive the development of creative solutions to address the world's challenges*”. It encourages the institutions to work on improving the educational environment to allow, achieve and consolidate this diversity. While this task is fundamental, in the case of gender diversity, it is also necessary to carry out specific actions that facilitate the number of women who access our higher engineering education institutions increase. Only in this way, we can achieve gender diversity in our own classrooms. In addition, our institutions, as generators of engineering knowledge, are the best places to carry them out.

In the EPS Polytechnic School of the UC3M we studied how this problem affects us. We also wanted to provide solutions, working with high-school girls of our environment. In 2016, we started with some activities, but in this course 2018/19 we have grouped and expanded them into a global project called STEM4GirlsUC3M which has five lines of action: (1) mentoring programs, (2) scenic arts and technology, (3) workshops and technological experiences, (4) contests and (5) sessions with relatives.

The paper is organized as follows. In section 2, we will contextualize this problem in our country (Spain) and in our university (UC3M). In section 3, we will talk about some of the most important programs that try to solve this problem. In section 4, we will describe the project that we have implemented. In section 5, we will provide some preliminary data on the impact of the actions already carried out. We will finish with the conclusions and future work in section 6.

2 SITUATION IN OUR NEAR ENVIRONMENT

According to the CRUE (Conference of Rectors of Spanish Universities), in the latest report, “The Spanish University in Figures 2016/2017” [8], the number of undergraduate female students represents 54% of all undergraduate university students. However, in recent years, it has been observed that its distribution in the different fields of knowledge is very unequal. The women students concentrate their preferences in Health and Welfare and in Education, and are reluctant to study Engineering and Architecture and, above all, Information and Communication Technologies. In the period 2008-2016 there has been a decrease in enrollment in the number of women in engineering education by 36.5%, which has led to a reduction of 2.7 points in their relative presence in the total of these teachings

(28.3% to 25.6%). This behavior is not something unique in our educational system, but it is a clear trend in many educational systems worldwide.

In the EPS of the UC3M, several degrees are offered in various engineering specialties, specifically, bioengineering, aerospace, industrial, telecommunications, computer science, and computer science and business administration. Only since the 2014/15 academic year, we have data disaggregated by gender that can be seen in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Distribution of women enrolled per specialties at EPS UC3M

As you can see, the specialty in Biomedical Engineering is the one that attracts the greatest number of women (around 60%), while Computer Science has the lowest percentage (around 14%). This degree experiments a slight, continuous decline in the last academic years. The global values at EPS-UC3M are below 23%, a figure that is far from the parity objective of 40%.

3 PROGRAMS TO PROMOTE STEM VOCATIONS IN GIRLS

In recent years, there have been numerous programs that try to stop the gender gap in STEM vocations and understand it better. Of course, they do it by working directly with girls. These initiatives have been promoted and funded by both public and private entities. Due to the limited extension of this article, it is not possible to review all of them in detail; we highlight those that have been implemented in Spain.

HypatiaProject (<http://www.expecteverything.eu/hypatia/>) is a project funded by the European Union whose main objective is that a large number of girls, between 13 and 18 years old, choose to study STEM disciplines. The project works in two lines. The first one is to bring these disciplines closer to the girls, so that they know them in the first person and see their many applications. The second one is to promote the participation of educational centers, museums, research institutions and industry in the promotion of the STEM model from a gender perspective. The project, completed in 2018, has developed a digital collection of modules with different types of

practices, scientific content workshops, informal discussions and meetings with professionals from the STEM disciplines aimed at adolescents, and which is ready to be used by teachers and schools. Finally, more than 69,000 teachers and 110,000 teenagers from Europe and Israel participated in the project.

InspiringGirls (<https://www.inspiring-girls.es/>) is an initiative created in the United Kingdom and deployed in Spain since 2017. Its strategy is to connect women's professions with girls, between 11 and 16 years old, through different formats: talks in their own schools; events called “speed networking” in which they offer 80-100 girls to meet 8-10 volunteers through short 10-minute meetings; finally sectoral thematic events so that they know the uniqueness of some STEM disciplines.

For Women in Science, L’Oreal-UNESCO (<http://bit.ly/2cKwOuG>), in addition to the well-known prizes to young women scientists and to support them in their trajectories so to be considered “role models”, this program also has an initiative for girls based on meetings called “Science Dating” that connects researchers and/or professionals with young girls between 13 and 16 years old.

STEMTalentGirl (<https://talent-girl.com/en/>) is a program of the Spanish Foundation ASTI that focuses on the talent and promotion of STEM vocations in girls through several initiatives. It offers “masterclasses” of relevant women of the STEM world and organizes “shadowing” sessions for girls of 14 and 15 years old. In these sessions, the girls accompany the women scientists and professionals in their place of work for two hours, so they can live with them how their job is.

Technovation Challenge (<https://technovationchallenge.org/>) is an annual entrepreneurship and technology competition that aims to inspire girls and young women, between 10 and 18 years old, to become leaders and innovators. This program started in 2009 in the US from the NGO Iridescent and since then, more than 15,000 girls from 100 countries have been part of it. The girls work in teams of up to 5 members, for 12 weeks (usually between January and April), to propose an entrepreneurial solution that addresses a nearby, social problem (health, education, peace, poverty, equality, environment ...). This solution is based on the development of a mobile app and a business model. The teams work supported by one or two mentors who help them throughout the process.

Women and Engineering of the Spanish Royal Academy of Engineers (<http://www.raing.es/es/content/acciones-mujer-e-ingenier>) is a project that aims to address the gender gap, both for young women engineers, through a mentoring program, as the problem of lack of vocations in girls. In this second line, it stands up its competition for teams of boys and girls between 12 and 16 years old, called TECHMI, where teams must build an engineering solution using a robotic kit. Girls must be at least half of the team and must led it. This year is the second edition.

In brief, all these programs have two main lines of action. The first one is to connect women scientists and STEM professionals with girls, to act as “role models”. This contact allows girls to better understand the work that these women do and to break

with acquired gender stereotypes. The second line is to encourage girls to work on STEM projects that solve social problems. This idea allows to understand what STEM fields are and what consist of, and to know the important social value that they have.

4 STEM4GIRLSUC3M PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Our project includes five actions that aim to provide high-school girls with the necessary information to choose, without gender stereotypes, their studies in the medium and long term. The participating girls are recruited advertising the project among high-schools in the region at Madrid. The following sections describe the different actions that are carried out.

4.1 Mentoring programs

In this action we have decided to integrate into some existing mentoring programs. In the first place, we have selected the international initiative Technovation Challenge. We train a team of mentors, made up of students from different disciplines, mostly women. The fact that mentors have an age close to the girls, leads to very valuable relationships and in many cases, they transcend much beyond the program itself. Our mentors also have the support of teachers who accompany them in their work, establishing mentoring relationships on two levels, university professor with university students, and university students with girls. In this program we participate since 2018.

Secondly, we have selected the STEM Talent Girl program, in which our women researchers carry out shadowing sessions at UC3M. Groups of girls accompany a woman researcher one afternoon, for two hours, to see her in her daily work environment and share their concerns with her. This activity has begun this year.

4.2 Scenic arts and technology

This action proposes the representation of a performance to raise, through the scenic arts, awareness among high school students about the problem of lack of STEM vocations in girls. It also wants to do a reflection about how the conscious and unconscious stereotypes may be influencing this problem.

Working jointly with the theater company “*The Cross Border Project*”, we have created a theater play entitled “*The girl who dreamed of Maxwell's equations*” which was represented on February 11, 2019 (International Day of Women and Girls in Science). After the play, several works of female researchers of the UC3M were presented in order to visualize their research activity. Unlike other actions, this one is aimed at girls and boys, so all together can reflect on the importance of women in science and technology, and contribute to the normalization of women's participation in these branches of knowledge.

4.3 Tech-Fridays: technological workshops and experiences

In this action, workshops are taught by professors and researchers from the EPS-UC3M, mostly women. Girls can choose between workshops on 3D bio-printing,

materials technology, aircraft construction, micro-robotics, cybersecurity, smart cities design, chatbots development, web accessibility, mobile communication networks, and internet of things. These activities are planned, as the previous one, within the celebration on February 11.

In the technological experiences, some relevant woman researchers, committed to equality in the STEM field, give talks to discover girls, in an entertaining way adapted to their age, what their research consists of and what practical applications it has. After these talks, the girls participate in various workshops organized by companies collaborating in our project.

4.4 Technovation Challenge regional contest

The Technovation Challenge program encourages to do regional contests in areas of the world where there are more than 10 teams competing. The EPS-UC3M has hosted the regional final at Madrid in 2018 and will also do it in 2019, on May 18. The final has a welcome session, then the teams of girls present their projects to a group of judges, while in parallel a technological fair is held, in which the teams can present their idea of entrepreneurship to the rest of the attendees. The event ends with an awards ceremony, in which the award-winning teams present their work to all the attendees.

4.5 Sessions for relatives

In most previous actions, welcome sessions and guided tours of the EPS' labs also take place. In this case, the target audience is mainly the relatives who accompany the girls to the activities. In this way, we also involve families in solving the problem and we can also answer their doubts and concerns, which are often shared and transmitted to their daughters.

5 FIRST RESULTS AND IMPACT OF THE PROGRAM

Although the program exists since this 2018/19 academic course, all the previous actions have been developed at least once. We believe that the success achieved with all of them, measured in terms of participation, have been very high.

In the mentoring program, Technovation Challenge, 3 coordinating teachers, 20 mentors and 30 mentees, who are girls from various high-schools, have participated. All our teams have delivered their projects. In the STEMTalentGirl program, 4 researchers participate, who have carried out shadowing sessions with 20 girls (5 girls each of them).

In the representation of the play performed on February 11, 2019, a total of 6 high-school centers participated, with 313 students.

Regarding technological workshops, in this academic course, 74 girls attended to a total of 7 workshops (the next course will be increased to 10 workshops). In the surveys we carried out, they valued the activity with 4.43 out of 5, highlighting as the most important the practical application of them, and as an improvement they asked

us to carry out more workshops. Their families have also highlighted the value of guidance that these workshops bring to the participants.

Regarding technological experiences, this course they involved 45 girls. At the date of delivery of this article, we still do not have results of surveys because the activity took place on April 5. The researchers who accompanied us on this occasion were Professor Karin Verspoor of the University of Melbourne in Australia and Professor Patricia Arias of the University of Mannheim in Germany.

Regarding the Technovation Challenge regional contest, in 2018 almost 400 girls participated in 94 teams. This year it will be held on May 18 and this time we have almost 600 girls confirmed to participate in it.

5.1 Activities just for girls

Most of our activities are just for girls. This condition raised us a lot of doubts when we launched the project. Several studies indicate that at early ages, girls have less leadership capacity than boys, due to their insecurities, so they do not work under equal conditions, and this makes that in teamwork they acquire a secondary role. Encouraged by these studies we have done it this way, having in mind to assess this point with our own studies.

The technological workshops, which we have offered just for girls, have been also offered for boys and girls during the rest of the academic year. A maximum of 15 people can attend the workshops and the selection criterion is the registration order. In Fig. 2 we can see the percentage of girls and boys who participated in these mixed workshops by specialty. Some specialties seem very little demanded by girls.

Fig. 2. Percentage of women in gender-mixed Tech-Friday

However, when we offered workshops for girls, we saw how some of them, at the beginning, did not seem to have a demand, but as the date of their completion approached they were filling up. And finally all of them were complete. Many of the girls told us in the workshops that they finally signed up because their parents encouraged them to do so and thinking that they had nothing better to do. However, most of them finished the workshops saying that they had learned a lot and that they did not imagine that these disciplines were so useful and fun. In Fig. 3 we see how the workshop records evolved by specialty during the registration period.

Fig. 3. Progress of registrations in Tech-Friday for girls

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The lack of vocations in engineering in general, and in particular in women, seems to be a trend that has been consolidated in recent years. This is a very serious problem for society in general, due to the importance of engineering and STEM disciplines in the sustainable development of the world. The higher education institutions that teach STEM studies must get involved in this problem, working with girls from an early age, otherwise these students will not reach our classrooms.

In this paper we describe the initiative that we are carrying out to alleviate the lack of STEM vocations in girls. We have created a program in which we involve our academic staff and our own students to help us. The program is being very supported within our university and very well received by the girls who participate in it.

We are aware that the real impact measure of these programs should include a monitoring, up to the university stage, of the girls who participate in them. This task is always complicated and difficult to automate without the direct cooperation of public education managers. However, our intention is to conduct surveys from time to time to participating girls to try to know the academic trajectory they are following and how the participation in our program has influenced them. It is a follow-up task that requires several years.

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